

Strategy to identify the most critical parts of a workflow for optimisation

Report on Milestone 3.4 of ELIXIR-STEERS

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Executive Summary

As part of the ELIXIR-STEERS project, Milestone 3.4 focuses on defining strategies for the identification and optimisation of computationally intensive and reusable components within life sciences workflows. The milestone builds primarily on the benchmarking activities of Task 3.3 and the orchestration enhancements of Task 3.4. Actions that affect efficiency and the environmental impact of a workflow are first presented in general terms. While interlinked, these are categorized in actions affecting data handling, the optimisation of single components, of workflows as a whole, the infrastructure used to deploy them, and the community aspects of uptake and dissemination.

The implementation of the strategy as a subset of the actions is supported by existing ELIXIR-related services and platforms. These include components of the [ELIXIR Research Software Ecosystem](#), and the production and use of software management plans through the [DSW](#) platform. Enhancements of platforms and services - developed within associated projects such as EVERSE, EuroScienceGateway and within STEERS - further enable the implementation of the strategies. The enhancements related to STEERS include the definition of metrics and tools such as TreeScript for low-level process monitoring, and benchmarking activities with ELIXIR Communities representatives. These are complemented by improvements to Galaxy's job caching mechanisms and the use of smarter job scheduling mechanisms with the integration of Pulsar and

the TPV Broker. Also affecting other workflow management systems, the use and extension of the GA4GH TES specification is described. The job scheduling enhancements have the added benefit of enabling better resource utilization reporting and environmental impact awareness among users.

Together, these efforts contribute to the broader ELIXIR goals of enabling reproducible, FAIR, and environmentally-responsible scientific computing.

Introduction

As life science research increasingly relies on complex, data-intensive computational workflows, ensuring their efficiency, reproducibility, and sustainability has become a strategic priority. Within the ELIXIR-STEERS project, Work Package 3 (WP3) focuses on enabling the adoption of best practices in research software and workflows. With a focus on workflows and their utilisation, this milestone focuses on efforts towards identifying critical parts of computational workflows for optimisation, environmental impact, and resource minimisation.

This milestone builds upon work from other work packages, with stronger interactions with the best practices gathered and defined within Work Package 2, as well as interactions with the different [ELIXIR Communities](#). Efforts from projects such as [EVERSE](#) and [EuroScienceGateway](#) are also influential to the developments described. This milestone specifically targets the identification of workflow components that are computationally intensive, and the ones that can be frequently reused.

ELIXIR-STEERS aims to enable researchers to reduce computational waste, select more efficient tools and resources, and make informed decisions about the environmental impacts of their analyses. The work described here represents efforts towards defining a common strategy for optimisation to be explored in the project and guide the development of further recommendations, tools, and services.

Methodology

This milestone represents a coordination effort to tackle different aspects of the production, execution and optimisation of computational workflows that can directly influence their efficiency, sustainability and reproducibility. The work primarily combines the efforts on technical benchmarking of workflows developed in Task 3.3, and the optimisations in workflow orchestration and execution developed in Task 3.4. Different layers of optimisation were explored, ranging from the identification of limitations that pertain to the workflows, to the ones that pertain to the infrastructure in which the workflows are executed.

To guide this process, we leveraged existing knowledge and tools, such as:

- Best practice guidelines and metrics exposed in the ELIXIR-STEERS Milestone report M2.2, "[Collection of existing best-practices and indicators for research software](#)"

- Technical benchmarking metrics described in the ELIXIR-STEERS Milestone report M3.3 “[Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified](#)”, particularly through the development and application of the Treecript tool, which was used to aid in the prioritisation of elements of a workflow execution for optimisation.

The data and insights from both tasks were brought together and discussed during Task 3.3 and 3.4 coordination meetings, allowing for cross-task analysis, validation of observations, and refinement of the strategy. These collaborative sessions ensured that benchmarking efforts informed optimisation priorities, and that the proposed strategy which was being developed, was grounded in measurable, technical evidence.

General Strategy

In alignment with WP3 objectives and tasks, particularly focusing on benchmarking, optimisation, and sustainable computational practices, the following strategies are proposed to make life sciences computational workflows (usually described in popular workflow languages like Nextflow, Snakemake, and Galaxy) more efficient, environmentally sustainable, and aligned with community best practices. The strategies tackle different aspects that can impact the efficiency of a workflow.

1. Data Management & Reduction

- **Intelligent Data Subsetting:** Incorporate preprocessing steps to filter datasets, processing only essential data to reduce computation time and resource usage. These can include input quality assessment steps to avoid unnecessary analyses of low-quality inputs.
- **Efficient Data Formats:** Encourage the adoption of compressed, indexed, and resource-efficient formats (e.g., CRAM, Zarr) through Software Management Plans, training materials, and workflow templates. It is preferential that the formats are also supported by efficient implementations of common toolboxes (e.g., bamtools, picard, sambamba, etc).
- **Intermediate File Cleanup:** Implement automated deletion of temporary intermediate files within workflows to minimise unnecessary storage consumption.
- **Data Deduplication:** While sometimes difficult to implement, it is valuable to integrate deduplication checkpoints in workflow systems to prevent redundant data processing across workflow executions.
- **Minimising Transfers:** Instead of moving large datasets to a central compute cluster, design infrastructure that allows for computation to occur where the data resides.

2. Algorithmic and Tool Optimisation

- **Algorithm Selection:** Prioritise the use of less computationally intensive software and algorithms (i.e. fewer inputs and outputs operations, or less memory and/or CPU time) where scientifically acceptable, as part of the benchmarking activities in Task 3.3.
- **Regular Software Updates:** Promote and support the use of up-to-date tools that offer improved efficiency, potentially highlighted through indicators developed in WP2.
- **Container and Dependency Optimisation:** Leverage minimal containers to streamline computational environments and reduce image sizes for faster and more efficient workflow execution.

3. Resource and Infrastructure Efficiency

- **Right-Sizing Resources:** Integrate automatic resource profiling and recommendations into workflow execution platforms (e.g., Nextflow, Galaxy), aligning with gathered reproducibility metadata represented in the form of [Workflow-Run RO-Crates](#).
- **Interruptible Compute Resource Utilisation:** Design software to tolerate interruptions and leverage lower-energy or unused cloud resources when appropriate. This includes provisions for the utilisation of Spot Instances/Preemptible virtual machines/Transient Virtual Servers from a variety of providers and allows for dynamic scalability of resource usage.
- **Selection of Green Data Centres:** Raise awareness and provide guidance within the Software Management Planning tool about selecting energy-efficient compute resources within the scope of the research project or facility.
- **Hardware Acceleration:** Benchmark and encourage the use of research software components that can leverage GPUs, FPGAs, or other accelerators for suitable bioinformatics tasks, thereby reducing energy consumption and execution times.

4. Workflow Design & Execution Optimisation

- **Job Caching and Provenance Reuse:** Implement job caching in workflow management systems to automatically reuse previous results where applicable.
- **Smarter Resumption:** Fully leverage resumption and checkpointing features to avoid unnecessary re-computation after workflow interruptions. This includes using workflow execution engines instead of *ad hoc* scripts.
- **Bundling Small Jobs:** Encourage the grouping of small tasks into larger jobs to reduce scheduling and data transfer overhead.
- **Local/Smart Execution of Lightweight Tasks:** Configure workflows to process small, low-resource tasks locally to the data to avoid the overhead of cluster submission.

- **Code and Process Profiling:** Establish regular profiling on workflows to continuously identify resource bottlenecks and opportunities for optimisation.

5. Awareness and Community Integration

- **Environmental Impact Reporting:** Develop and integrate workflow reporting features that display estimated energy consumption and resource usage to researchers after the execution of the analysis or even in real-time when systems permit it.
- **Software Management Plans:** Promote the inclusion of sustainability and resource-efficiency considerations within Software Management Plans, supported by the Data Stewardship Wizard ([DSW](#)).
- **Community Dissemination:** Ensure that optimised workflows and benchmarking results are shared via [WorkflowHub](#), [OpenEBench](#), training materials, and community platforms to promote widespread adoption.

Strategy within STEERS services and platforms

Several of the strategies described above can be approached with the use of ELIXIR-related services, and with special focus on services involved in the ELIXIR-STEERS project. Several aspects of data management that can impact a computational workflow are already described in the [RDMkit](#). These include guidance on [data quality](#) and [data transfer](#). Quality indicators of research software, as well as factors impacting the development of tools are being defined within the activities of WP2 and, in conjunction with the [EVERSE project](#), are to be made available in the emerging [RSQkit](#). Services such as [bio.tools](#) improve the findability of alternative and emerging tools, while [WorkflowHub](#) allows researchers to share and find optimised workflows.

The use of Software Management Plans, with the potential to support tools used in computational workflows or even entire workflows themselves, is further facilitated by the [DSW platform](#). Researchers and tool providers can find knowledge models to modify or directly produce software management plans in the [DSW Registry](#), including the [software management plan knowledge model](#) created in the context of ELIXIR-STEERS.

More specifically, from the ELIXIR-STEERS Task 3.3 perspective, a software has been developed to obtain time series of a set of technical metrics associated with the processes spawned during a computational analysis, which enable the assessment of efficiency and environmental impact of software executions. This software is [Treecript \(Process Tree Metrics Transcriptor\)](#), which gathers low-level technical metrics from Linux processes used to derive high-level indicators, including computational carbon footprint estimations. The [STEERS T3.3 Technical Metrics live document](#) describes the low and high-level community-led metrics.

Analysing the collected metrics of scientific research executions enables researchers to assess the impact and usage of the underlying software used by those researchers; executing the very same

analysis several times in order to gather accurate metrics requires ensuring workflow reproducibility and promoting reuse. Additionally, the interpretation of the gathered time series of the technical metrics can help identify the most critical components of complex executions, like workflows, providing insights for optimisation and improvement.

Importantly, Treecript has been designed with interoperability and platform integration in mind. It will eventually be integrated into the OpenEBench platform, where it will serve as a foundational component for extending the platform's capabilities in technical benchmarking. This integration will enable OpenEBench to not only compare and assess research software and workflows based on community-defined quality indicators but also to operationalise the optimisation strategies defined in this milestone. In doing so, it strengthens OpenEBench's capabilities in evaluating the performance and efficiency of computational life sciences tools and workflows.

From the ELIXIR-STEERS Task 3.4 perspective, effort has been allocated to enhance workflow orchestrators in both resource utilisation, optimisation and minimisation. By both increasing awareness in resource consumption and also allowing for the reuse of inputs, outputs and intermediate files, the enhancements allow for identification of resource-consuming steps at the same time as providing a flexible approach for different workflows and workflow languages.

In particular, we are enhancing the job cache mechanism in Galaxy, a feature that avoids redundant computation by reusing results from previously executed jobs with the same inputs and parameters. Previously, the cache relied solely on internal dataset IDs, which limited reuse when identical files were uploaded multiple times. As part of Task 3.4, we extended the system to also match input datasets by content hash, and expanded cache searches to include public Galaxy histories. These improvements are particularly beneficial in training settings, where many users run the same analyses repeatedly.

Additionally, Galaxy exploits Pulsar, a lightweight job execution engine developed within the Galaxy Project, to enable the remote execution of tools and workflows. It plays a central role in distributing compute workloads across heterogeneous infrastructures while maintaining a consistent user experience within Galaxy. One of the key benefits of using Pulsar is its ability to minimise data movement by allowing analyses to run directly on remote endpoints located closer to the data source. This approach significantly reduces the need to transfer large datasets across networks, improving performance and lowering bandwidth costs. As part of the [EuroScienceGateway project](#), numerous Pulsar endpoints have been developed and integrated into the European Pulsar Network, further expanding its capacity and geographic reach. By bringing computation to the data, Pulsar enhances efficiency, scalability, and sustainability across national and European research infrastructures.

Moreover, the [TPV Broker](#) is an API component developed within the EuroScienceGateway project to enhance Galaxy's existing Total Perspective Vortex (TPV) mechanism, and has also been identified in STEERS as a mechanism to tackle resource usage efficiency by workflows. While TPV has successfully supported large-scale job scheduling for a global user base, the TPV Broker introduces new features aimed at improving efficiency and resource utilisation. It enables real-time monitoring of usage across distributed computing endpoints, integrates geographical metadata to optimise data locality in job allocation, and incorporates advanced meta-scheduling strategies

evaluated through simulation. The system relies on producer scripts deployed at Pulsar endpoints to collect scheduler metrics and publish them to a centralised time-series database, while consumer scripts used by Galaxy servers query this data to inform scheduling decisions. These developments support more balanced load distribution, lower execution times, and improved overall performance.

In ELIXIR's ELIXIR On Cloud ecosystem, workflow jobs are sent to individual compute centres through implementations of the Global Alliance for [Genomics and Health's \(GA4GH\) Task Execution Service \(TES\)](#) API specification, deployed at each participating Node. This specification allows the declaration of resource requirements for a given job. Specifically, clients can enforce upper limits for the number of used CPUs, memory and disk space, as well as the acceptable use of preemptible worker instances (where supported) and backend-specific parameters (e.g., for particular GPUs). In the federated setup of the ELIXIR On Cloud, individual TES instances are typically not addressed directly. Rather, a centrally deployed gateway TES implementation (<https://github.com/elixir-cloud-aai/proTES>) receives all tasks and relays them to an appropriate TES. This setup makes the ELIXIR On Cloud easily amenable to the integration of sustainable practices via the gateway's middleware engine. To this end, we have already implemented a middleware that attempts to minimise data transfers by sending incoming jobs to the TES instance nearest to the input data. During the remainder of the ELIXIR-STEERS project, we will aim to create similar middlewares for optimisation strategies such as right-sizing resources, job caching and environmental impact reporting. While not all of the optimisation strategies listed in the previous section can be addressed with this setup (e.g., local execution of lightweight tasks), importantly, it is agnostic of the upstream client and therefore allows overriding decisions made by workflow developers or workflow engines. In some cases, supporting these strategies may require extension of the TES specification, either within the scope of the ELIXIR On Cloud ecosystem, or by promoting specification updates through raising issues and pull requests in the TES GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas>; disclaimer: contributor Alexander Kanitz is a member of the GA4GH TES product champions team).

Conclusion

Through an iterative methodology, partners were able to:

- 1) Exchange knowledge and strategies from different services and platforms towards a more aligned set of categories for workflow optimisation. These include items on workflow limitations versus infrastructure limitations, the tools and potential metrics for reporting on resource utilisation, and aspects of data management and handling that impact workflow efficiency.
- 2) Initiate the validation of different approaches proposed against initial benchmarking data from selected workflows described in the ELIXIR-STEERS milestone report M3.3 "[Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified](#)" contributed by ELIXIR Communities.

- 3) Initiate the necessary alignment in metrics and feature prioritisation between the benchmarking efforts and the resource optimisation efforts in workflow orchestrating systems.

The strategies and tools described here can be generally applied to computational workflows to enable the identification of resource-demanding components and steps. It also allows for a more comprehensive view on workflow efficiency and resource utilisation, taking into account different layers of potential optimisation: from workflow design to infrastructure implementation.

Further work will be conducted to enable implementation and use of the general strategies. This includes further implementation of optimisations in workflow management systems as already initiated and described in this milestone, as well as continuation of benchmarking efforts. Through continued interactions with ELIXIR Communities, additional benchmarking will aid in informing enhancements to the STEERS-related services, as well as driving the uptake of services and best practices by the different ELIXIR Communities.